

Profiling Academic Research on what is Being Sought in Initial Teacher Education Gender Wise

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ABSTRACT: This article is mainly focused on what is happening with university structures, at least in the aspects related to the pedagogy of gender, specifically transgender, provided to pre-service vocational students. Universities are hyper-regulated spaces in which, in an invisible way, there are spaces of censorship in the production of knowledge and the selection of topics of interest for research and learning. Vocational teacher formation has constituted a whole scenario of being, in which the gender diversity and especially Transgender is not contemplated. Initial teacher education in Colombia seems to be monolithic. Teaching education does not include topics or contents that deals with gender, least Transgenderism. The monolithic construction of who supposed to be “The English teacher” is an evident problem in the initial vocational teacher formation. Teacher formation is dis-gendered, denies not only the existence of “genders” but moreover the existence of Transgender “individuals” in classroom. This article traces back the meaning attributed to transgenderism in particular teaching practices, specifically in vocational training classroom, from some previous studies until ELT teachers’ and students’ beliefs, thoughts, perceptions, and interpretations about transgenderism. Additionally, by looking into elements that have been left unattended or unsaid in previous works concerned with gender, the integration of transgender teachers’ & students’ personal and professional experiences will be an ally ship not only on how to intervene when transphobia occurs, but also in the consolidation of the future transgender teachers’ identity.

KEYWORDS: transgender, teacher formation, transgender teachers, teaching transgender.

INTRODUCTION

This article is based on the need to problematize the understanding from the formative and educative field, the experiences of learning and formation of the future transgender teachers, in Bultler words (2002) “some teachers close to media intellectuals remain deaf and blind to the views of students, minorities, exercising a power of interference in which the persons ignores their capabilities” (p.43)

The before mention ideas foster to think about the relevance in the formation of pre-service vocational students and their teachers about what being a transgender individual means. Providing them not only theoretical and pedagogical foundations, but through life experiences and previous research proposals for teaching gender, thoughts and teachings from some transgender students and some experts in the subject. The problem itself aims to enquire on how to explore and make visible the diversity of our students in our educational and academic contexts, this due to they are invisible because current context learners and teachers are dis gendered, apolitical.

Although there are a large number of publications on gender studies, there is little academic research on transgender studies in the area of teacher education. This study aims to reveal what, when, where and who constitute academic work in the research on the prospects of training for transgender students. This exercise was based on the need to problematize from the understanding of the formative and educative field, the experiences in learning and formation of the future transgender teachers.

A set of data recorded in 50 research articles was configured with primary documents taken from four databases of two portals, addressing the analysis on research papers about; “Teaching Transgender” “Promoting Transgender Ed” “Transgender Education” “Transgender in classroom” “Preservice teachers formation in transgender” exploring major topics and arguments in the field of transgenderism in pedagogy. Drawing on 50 articles retrieved from the databases like, Web of Science, Justor, Tailor & Francis, Scopus and EBSCO;

The findings revealed some communalities that were grouped into tables of categories and patterns that allowed me to pose and delimit a problem. It was also found that research on this topic began in 2000 and some milestones of emerging research were

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recorded. I also identified the most prolific organizations and authors in which the United States, Canada, Mexico, Spain, Brazil, Chile, Africa and Spain occupy prominent places.

Geopolitical Positioning

To get a better understanding of this exercise was it necessary to search voices from all around the world, so the research was widely done. The following representations of the global map with the authors of the articles will show the global positioning.

Figure 1. Geopolitical positioning (first approximation)

This picture depicts the precedence of the first twenty articles, in this first search the vast majority of the studies found came from EEU and Canada, further I will show a circular graphic to get a general perspective about the precedence of the information.

Figure 2. Geopolitical positioning (second approximation)

In the same of thoughts the figure number two depicts the still prevalence of north authors, then was necessary to go deep in the search to find out relevant authors from south.

Figure 3. Geopolitical positioning (third and last approximation approximation)

The figure number three shows the results of searching articles in Spanish, the literature about transgender or transgenderisms in teacher formation in America and specifically in Colombia is really scarce, the next circular graphic represents the amount of information encountered in the different geopolitical locations.

Graphic 1. Authors & Geopolitical positioning

The Graphic 1 shows the growing availability of literature about transgender studies not only in EEU and Canada but in Europe, and the scarce amount of research done in Latin America and Africa.

Continuing with the profiling exercise I will explain how the research analysis was conducted in terms of comprehend the informed literature found in the articles conducive to the elaboration of the problem.

METHODOLOGY

The process started using some search phrases related to my research interest in the research engine of different data bases, to exemplify the previous procedure, below one of the four tables done (one for the four databases consulted) to evidence the exercise done.

Table 1. Data base, search phrases plus data bases filiation by topic

Data base	Search Phrases	Results
	Promoting Transgender Ed.	PARKER; 2009. Building Literature to promote Trans culture.
		ABBOTT; 2009. Transgender Biographies & literature.
		WENTLING; 2008. Including Transgender topics in university classes.

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Transgender Education	FREITAS; 2017. Teachers & Students Dichotomies in gender discourses.
	CHEUNG; 2000. The deficit model that victimizes LGBTQ SS.
	LEONARDI; 2015. Skilling teachers to ensure inclusive classes.
Teaching Transgender	ALEXANDER; 2008. Blurring trans through hetero normal discourses.
	PLANELLA; 2017 – Enhancing Trans Education to teaching
	HALBERSTAM; 2017 – Rethink the meaning of identity & body
Transgender in classroom	RAND; 2003. Interpreting new entities in classroom.
	REIS; 2004. Untangle rooted ideas about “normal” and “natural”
	WHITLOCK; 2010. Engaging queer pedagogies to School curricula.
Pre service teachers formation in transgender	SHELTON; 2015. Students dropping out, in spite of supportive legislation
	NAIDOO; 2014. Pervasive Heterosexism and heteronormativity in ELT.
	NAUGLER; 2010. Bullying as Heteronormative hegemonic Masculinities.
Vocational formation in transgender	Santiago Perez- Bedoya (2016) The relationship between attitudes towards and knowledge of sexual diversity
	MEYER; 2018. Fears interfering in integral development of LGBTQ SS.
	JOHNSON; 2018. Analysis of transgender movement.

The table one shows the articles gotten after surfing the in data base with the different search phrases.

Followed by the previous surfing exercise, fifty articles emerged from the search. As it is affirmed by Castañeda (2012, p.11) “Research profiling studies are more interesting in finding out about patterns in literature considered as a whole patterned body” and the main concern of this exercise is the analysis of the articles in terms of finding “The not Yet”, I moved towards the next stage, the analysis of the information.

In the way of finding the best procedure to do the analysis I considered suitable to use the technique Color Coding; according to Hix, James & Jacob (1995) the color-coded display of information permits the reader the association of particular referents in an immediate way allowing them to perform data-analysis tasks that were before impossible. In other words, the color-coding technique serves as a strong referent for analyzing the information in this profiling exercise in order to draw on problem statements and then narrow them in problematic facts as it is shown in the next table:

Table 2. Article, Problem statements & Problematic Facts

Article	Problem Statement	Problematic Facts
1. Pedagogías Transgénero	Violence, exclusion, vulnerability are some problems that are not being taken into account in the educational curricula.	
2. Trans A Quick And Quiry Account Of Gender Variability	The problem the author highlights relies on how understand gender variability, social change and new political formations in terms of rethink the meaning of identity & body.	
3. Trans* Diversidad De Identidades Y Roles De Género	The problem the authors cover is how contribute to avoid stigmatization of socially vulnerable transgender groups through	

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	activities that can be organized in any community and that foster on how to visualize and project the presence of these transgender groups in society.	Lack of training in Transgender pedagogies.
4. Indígenas Homosexuales	The main concern of the author is to make a trace back in some indigenous communities with the intention of resurrect the narratives of their homosexual lives.	
5. Teaching Transgender	The problem entails on how to find an approach towards including Transgender topics in university classes,	
6. Trans Matters in Education: Insights from Students	The problem arose in this article focuses on how to interpret new abstract entities in classroom if someone has changed the categories because of a transit.	
7. Transgender Rhetorics: Sex And Gender	The problem the author expresses relies on how throughout our discourses we kept returning to hetero normal definitions about gender, without taking into consideration the transits transgender subjects do.	
8. Elementary teachers' experiences with LGBTQ-inclusive education: Addressing fears with knowledge to improve confidence and practices.	The problem of this author highlights on how teachers fears are interfering in the free integral development of LGBTQ students.	Research on transgender teachers is non-existent
9. The sociocultural factors that influence a novice teacher's LGBT activism	The author problematizes this article finding an answer about why LGBT students from The University of Georgia are dropping out, in spite of legislation that discriminates against those who do not fit normative notions of sexuality and gender, is established.	
10. Religion-related stigma and discrimination experienced by lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender students at a South African rural-based university	The author sets the problem of this article on pursuing the consequences some students do not attend specific classes, do not terminate their studies and even attempt suicide.	
11. Teaching beyond the deficit model: gay and lesbian issues among African Americans, Latinos, and Asian.	The author expresses the problem of this article in terms of how the selected literature focuses heavily on the deficit aspects and seldom identifies the strengths of LGBT African Americans, Latinos, and Asian Americans cultures.	
12. 'Keeping things straight': the representation of sexualities in life orientation textbooks.	The author focuses the problem not only on how Heterosexism and heteronormativity are pervasive in the society, but also to what degree are they present in Life Orientation (LO) textbooks.	Gender Polices (somewhat restrictive and harmful)
13. Beyond Acceptance: Serving the Needs of Transgender Students.	The problem of this article relies on examine the ways that transgender students' experiences differ from teachers narratives in co-educational environments.	

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14. Teaching Transgender Literature	The author addresses de problem to the lack of knowledge about transgender lives, and proposes transgender biographies to study the variety of transgender experiences in literature.	
15. Gender Variant and Transgender Issues in a Professional Development Book Group.	The problem this document focuses on how teachers can gain understanding necessary not only to foster and support gender variants and transgender students, but also in finding the way to incorporate this experiences into their curriculum in a meaningful way.	
16. Affirm gender and sexual diversity within the school community	The authors concerns rely on the fact most teachers want their classrooms to be safe places for all gender and sexual identities but few have the training and skills to make that a reality.	Lack models of nontraditional gender training.
17. Wearing pink as a stand against bullying: Why we need to say more.	The main problem in the article is given in terms of switching the features of masculine socialization, male-on-male bullying secures the reproduction of an aggressive and heteronormative hegemonic Masculinity.	
18. Teaching Transgender History, Identity, and Politics	The problem in this article states about untangle deeply rooted ideas about what is “normal” and “natural,” in terms of changing someone sex, emplacing students with empathetic objectivity with the purpose of understanding other´s position.	
19. Social Equity in the New 21st-Century America.	The author´s purpose in this paper is to examine the transgender movement as a mean to eliminate transgender oppression from the workplace promoting with this transgender awareness and education to the social equity.	
20. Getting queer: Teacher education, gender studies, and the cross-disciplinary quest for queer pedagogies.	The author looks to explore intersections and tensions among queer theory, teacher education, and identities/identifications, engaging a particular way of looking at curriculum, pedagogy, and the self.	
21. Being Transgender: The Experience of Transgender Identity Development	The problem relies on Transgender individuals often lack models of nontraditional gender to aid them in their identity development.	
22. La formación del profesorado en género	Detectar mediante el análisis de técnicas narrativas expresiones y discursos que muestren las representaciones mentales que el profesorado en formación mantiene sobre el binomio género poder	
23. La relación entre actitudes y conocimientos sobre diversidad sexual.	El problema del artículo radica en cómo aportar nuevas pistas para optimizar los programas de formación docente a fin de luchar contra la discriminación y la intimidación del estudiantado homosexual y bisexual.	

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<p>24. Can We Teach Transgender Issues in Vocational Training?</p>	<p>This article problematizes in a specific teaching practice that brings transgenderism into a vocational training classroom, defeating the notions that it cannot be done, it is too complicated, or it is controversial. The article also discusses how personal experiences with transphobia can be used to act out different responses and vicariously learn the consequences of the different alternatives.</p>	<p>The lack of life experiences and surfeit of prejudices is a barrier to Transgender integral development.</p>
<p>25. Developing Allies to Transgender and Gender-Nonconforming Youth: Training for Counselors and Educators</p>	<p>Lack of training regarding transgender youth leaves educators unprepared to become allies to this disenfranchised community and attend to their needs. This article explores the pedagogical strategies of two professional workshop models (GLSEN Houston training and the Gender Infinity practitioner training), which provide skills and resources for educators.</p>	
<p>26. Wearing My Identity: A Transgender Teacher in the Classroom</p>	<p>In educational systems, transgender issues are becoming increasingly relevant as both students and staff “come out” as transgender, and as young people explore non-normative gender expression. In comparison to the empirical and theoretical discussions on gay, lesbian, and bisexual youth issues in education, research on transgender youth is sparse, and academic research on transgender teachers is non-existent.</p>	
<p>27. Making It Better for Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender Students through Teacher Education: A collaborative self-study</p>	<p>Teacher education programs have a critical role in helping incoming teachers develop a deeper understanding of lesbian, gay, bisexual, but not transgender issues, their moral and legal obligations to counter on avoiding bullying.</p>	<p>The need of humanizing classroom in terms of gender variability.</p>
<p>28. The transgender awareness webinar: Reducing transphobia among undergraduates students.</p>	<p>The problems were how to find a way to educate undergraduates about transgender individuals reducing trans phobic attitudes specifically towards reducing transphobia stigma towards transgender individuals.</p>	
<p>29. Avenue T: using film as entrée in teaching about transgender</p>	<p>Educators from a variety of disciplines include the concept of transgender and multiple gender identities in course curricula. The ‘T’ (denoting the specific inclusion of transgender) often is given less pedagogical attention than is sexual orientation, and the transgender concept often is taught in the context of sexual orientation.</p>	
<p>30. Teaching Transgender Toolkit: A Facilitator's Guide to Increasing Knowledge, Decreasing Prejudice & Building Skills</p>	<p>The problem relies on several limitations included “the ever-changing language around gender identities” and the lack of specific focus on schools discrimination.</p>	

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<p>31. Transgender Teachers: The Personal, Pedagogical, and Political</p>	<p>How to explore transgender teachers' navigations; the personal, pedagogical, political, the survival and transition strategies they developed to become intelligible within their schools. They developed counter narratives to challenge traditional discourses of trans invisibility, silence, shame, and fear.</p>	
<p>32. Teaching Transgender in Women's Studies</p>	<p>How teaching transgender task is complicated by a plethora of factors, including our own complex sexual orientation, the students' relative lack of life experience and surfeit of prejudices, the tendency of some Women's Studies courses to emphasize a gender dichotomy and a second wave feminist viewpoint, and of course the inherent perplexities of the trans issue itself.</p>	
<p>33. Teach to Reach: Addressing Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender Youth Issues in the Classroom</p>	<p>The author places the discussion within the context of learning environments and presents ways in which pre-service and in-service teachers can help create safe and equitable spaces for all learners. Presented are various classroom strategies, activities, and resources for educators to tap into and utilize.</p>	
<p>34. "The Changers and the Changed": Preparing Early Childhood Teachers to Work With Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender Families</p>	<p>The problem the author covers relies on how to provide professional teacher formation to pre service early childhood students, given the fact that just as heterosexual families require child care to enable work and want high-quality early childhood education to enhance their children's development, LGBT families experience the same needs and desires for their children.</p>	<p>The segregation practices in the school affect negatively transgender students' lives.</p>
<p>35. Transexualidad y Transgénero: una perspectiva bioética.</p>	<p>La autora problematiza en su artículo como la transexualidad como práctica y categoría médica es un fenómeno atravesado por cuestiones de bioética. Categorías médicas patologizantes, como "transexualismo" o "transvestismo", operan como productoras y reguladoras de la 'verdad' del género.</p>	
<p>36. La transexualidad desde la mirada de la sociología del cuerpo.</p>	<p>El problema de ésta investigación se enmarcó en el cómo encontrar la manera de presentar la sociología del cuerpo como un marco analítico conceptual para entender el proceso de la corporeidad subversiva como lo es la transexualidad.</p>	
<p>37. La modificación del cuerpo transgénero: experiencias y reflexiones</p>	<p>El artículo problematiza acerca de cómo los docentes Transgenero dan cuenta de procesos de modificación efectiva, como intentan apropiarse de una feminidad socialmente aceptada, al colocar sobre su carne una realidad distinta y abrir con ello múltiples posibilidades que muestran una sensibilidad alterna y filtran el acontecimiento de la diferencia. Se explica</p>	<p>The lack in knowledge about gender diversity.</p>

	cómo tales procesos otorgan otras identidades en la práctica cotidiana.	
38. La politización del cuerpo: Subjetividades Trans en resistencia	La problemática se plantea en términos de indagar por la experiencia del cuerpo trans (transgénero o transexual), cuya “artificialidad” interpela los órdenes del sujeto en la modernidad. Así, la intervención singular sobre un cuerpo se torna en politización macro en el ámbito de lo público.	
39. Géneros, Transgéneros: Hacia Una Noción Bidimensional De La Injusticia.	El artículo problematiza tomando como paradigma el modelo bidimensional de justicia de Nancy Fraser , argumenta que los dispositivos de marginación que operan sobre las personas transgéneras tienen como punto de origen tanto una precaria valoración cultural como una economía política regulada sobre la base de una división del trabajo fundada en la sexualidad.	
40. El Transgenerismo. Detección Y Actuación Como Prevención De La Violencia De Género	El problema se enmarca en la necesidad de buscar respuestas ante la violencia cotidiana que amenaza continuamente nuestra convivencia (violencia de género, violencia escolar, etc.) proponiendo ideas que puedan ayudar a la mejora de la situación. Si hablamos de violencia de género y escolar ambos temas se pueden localizar en las escuelas en torno, entre otros, a un concepto relativamente nuevo y poco estudiado: el transgenerismo.	
41. Democratización de las identidades, transgenerismo y malestares de género	La problemática del presente artículo se enfoca en la necesidad de estudiar la relación o relaciones que se dan entre la formación y la definición de las identidades (individuales y colectivas) . En este sentido, se pretende demostrar que, para que se pueda dar una democratización de estas identidades, es preciso abandonar la concepción dicotómica que las caracteriza y desplegar una consideración de estas como realidades fluidas accesibles para toda la ciudadanía democrática en la que las aportaciones teóricas del transgenerismo pueden ser útiles para pensar de manera más inclusiva nuestra vida.	Curricula in universities are blind against sexual discrimination and gender inequality.
42. Hacia una educación no sexista: tensiones y reflexiones desde la experiencia de escuelas en transformación	La autora problematiza las tensiones que se han vivido en dos ámbitos centrales en los que se manifiesta la reproducción de lógicas de discriminación sexual y de inequidad de género en el espacio educativo , como son el currículum y la convivencia escolar.	
43. Educação Física Escolar: Os Impactos Sociais Na Vida De Pessoas Transexuais Em Belém Do Pará.	El autor intenta comprender los impactos positivos o negativos que las practicas segregadoras en asignaturas como la educación física, tienen en la vida social de personas Transgenero.	

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44. Protocolo de actuación en los centros educativos ante la incorporación de alumnado transgénero.	El autor de este protocolo intenta coordinar las intervenciones necesarias, a corto y medio plazo, ante la incorporación, detección o conocimiento de estudiantes transgénero, de manera que se promueva, entre los miembros de la comunidad educativa, una percepción de mayor comprensión, manejo y control de estas situaciones.	
45. Letramento crítico para diferença: percepção de professores sobre o currículo de língua inglesa no Brasil	El autor centra sus intención investigativa en torno a la percepción de los profesores brasileños sobre el currículo de lengua en la formación de estudiantes de pregrado, enfatizando la cuestión de la diversidad de género; Los profesores creen que ellos no fueron adecuadamente preparados para lidiar con la diversidad en el contexto educativo, pero algunos tratan este tópico intuitivamente desde la perspectiva (género / etnicidad) es evidente entonces la necesidad de revisión de los programas de enseñanza de lengua inglesa en la educación superior para cubrir cuestiones relacionadas con la diversidad de género.	Binary perception of gender makes invisible the fluid gender variability.
46. Experiencia Transgenero más allá de la bivalencia	Las relaciones de poder en el aula inclusiva develan sesgos circunstanciales localizados en la subjetividad de algunos docentes.	
47. Queer English Language Teacher Identity - A Narrative Exploration in Colombia	The problem relies on Transgender individuals often lack models of nontraditional gender to aid them in their identity development.	
48. Narratives to Reach: Addressing Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and transgender Youth Issues in the EFL Classroom	The tendency of some Women’s Studies courses to emphasize a gender dichotomy and a second wave feminist viewpoint, and of course the inherent perplexities of the trans issue itself.	
49. Getting queer: Teacher education, gender studies, and the cross-disciplinary quest for queer pedagogies.	The author looks to explore intersections and tensions among queer theory, teacher education, and identities/identifications, engaging a particular way of looking at curriculum, pedagogy, and the self.	
50. La formación del profesorado en género	Detectar mediante el análisis de técnicas narrativas expresiones y discursos que muestren las representaciones mentales que el profesorado en formación mantiene sobre el binomio género poder.	

Following the analysis process, the profiling exercise allowed to encounter some problematic facts (P.F). Some of those P.F point towards the “not yet” in terms of finding new perspectives to contribute in the formation of future teachers about transgenderism. Forward a graphic that entails the most relevant P.F encountered in the scrutiny.

Chart 1. “There are grand narratives associated to transgender students who will be language teachers in the future” & “the discursive mechanisms now used to perpetuate and promote cisgender as monolithically option”.

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Chart 2. Authors who consider tendencies Normalization of teachers practices seems the learners to be Genderless.

Graphic 2. Relevant Problematic facts

The Graphic 2 contains the most relevant problematic facts

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From the previous profiling exercise it is possible to abstract the next ideas as the most relevant or significant in this review process to problematize;

- 1- Transgender pre-service teachers often lack models of nontraditional gender to aid them in their teacher identity development.
- 2- It is necessary to characterize which specific teaching practices could bring transgenderism into a vocational training classroom, towards defeating the notions that it cannot be done, it is too complicated, or it is controversial. The experiences with transphobia could be a worthy source to act out different responses and sensitize the learners about the validity of being different.
- 3- Pre service teacher's needs in transgender formation is causing drop outs, the lack of training regarding transgenderism leaves educators unprepared to become allies to this disenfranchised community.
- 4- Research on transgender youth is sparse, and academic research on transgender teachers is non-existent.
- 6- It is necessary to find a way to educate pre-service teachers about transgender individuals reducing transphobic attitudes specifically reducing transphobia stigma towards transgender individuals.
- 7- Transgender education often is given less pedagogical attention than it's sexual orientation, and the transgender concept often is taught in the context of sexual orientation thus it is necessary to find a strategy to switch these misconceptions.
- 9- It is needed to explore transgender teachers' navigations; the personal, pedagogical, political, the survival and transition. Teachers need to develop counter narratives to change traditional discourses of transgender invisibility, silence, shame, and fear strategies to become intelligible within their schools.
- 10- Try to find a way to include transgender in teachers formation curricula is urgent by a plethora of factors, the misunderstanding of our own complex sexual orientation, the students' relative lack of life experience and surfeit of prejudices, and of course the inherent perplexities of the lack of formation in transgender issues itself.
- 11- It is necessary to innovate in various classroom strategies, activities, and resources for educators to tap into and utilize the context of learning environments to present ways in which pre-service and in-service teachers can help create safe and equitable spaces for all learners.

CONCLUSIONS

The exercise of reflection done based on this review aimed to build my personal posture about the imperative need of teaching transgender in the pedagogical field for pre-service teacher's formation. It was a guiding light not only to problematize taking advantage of all literature analyzed, but learning on how to approach my problematic properly.

On the other hand, I could affirm research projects about teaching Transgender to pre-service teachers in Colombian are of vital importance given the conditions of marginalization and inattention these young individuals are facing. The lack in literature related to Transgender individuals in classroom, especially in Latin America, booster the need to offer a realistic and reliable theoretical support to those who are interested and concerned in recognize and make visible transgender future teachers not only as future formers of humans but, as human beings.

Thus, it is fundamental to continue doing a deep and upheld research to provide information, tools and strategies that aim to generate programs and solutions in benefit of any transgender subjects, this will provide helpful alternatives that will be reflected not only in the future transgender teachers' close contexts but to all those teachers who recognize in the difference a possibility to build a healthy leaning environment.

In the same line of thoughts this lit review exercise leads me to invite ELT educators and vocational students to guide their classes for teaching English in a more inclusive way in order to take into account proper procedures to identify and handle alternatives for all diverse students, giving transgender people not only the opportunity to have an integral development but also the protections and facilities to make them feel respected accepted and worthy, to be seen as a person endowed with lots of values and capacities.

Britzman (2002) asserts on the way in which normality becomes an enormously imperceptible element in the classroom, about how pedagogy itself can intervene to make these limits and the obstacles of normality perceptible, (p.33). In the previous ideas the problem lies in wanting to break with the idea of the other as suspicious subject, dangerous, fearful, infectious, and worrying, in constant threat to the rest of the population.

It is claimed therefore not only investigating the policies and special plans in our country for this population but also promote their rights. It is important to think that young Transgender students deserve a well-considered valuation of equality and rights as it is defined in - The Universal Human rights Declaration – which includes among others, the right to the education, identity, safety, free association expression, health and family, all the relevant ones enclosing and applicable to the rights of the homosexual youth.

Mérida, 2003, summarizes the proposal of Britzman (2002) saying: "the classroom can be transformed into a space that favors social change if the teaching practice conjugates a revision of the authoritarian structure that usually defines its strategies and, above all, with the daily questioning of normative heterosexuality through transgressive learning mode". The binary position between the normal and the abnormal needs to be deconstructed although not through the reconstruction of the subjects located in the abnormal

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category but through exploring a new political imaginary in which diverse alliances can be forged between people with gender diversity. Alliances that can start and innovate the forms of social and intellectual discipline of the academy (Wiegman, 2002, p.74).

It is relevant in this problematization to understand how to get away from victimization and normalization, this achieve could be gotten by gaining rights over the heteronormative formation, but what is really worrying is how to eliminate the discourses that maintain those power relations. The logic and political utility of a deconstruction of collective categories competes with the logic of defending them, the invitation would be to continually deconstruct the traps of identity.

According to Foucault (1977) It is understood that sexual science are historical and social products and that the purpose of joint them is related, fundamentally with the social control. The same man-woman binomial excludes other possibilities and definitively denies the constructive nature of the world's gender; the institutions are structured according to this logic. Thus, the definitions of social organizations are based on this binary assumption, (p.28).

Heteronormativity involves so many practices, that at this moment it is unimaginable a world where this compendium of hegemonic norms are not dominant, the new policies are not only opposed to the idea of normality, but the same idea of normal behavior. Transsexual subjects do not want to be normal, do not want to be in the dynamics of good and correct, either in the scale of heterosexual, this scale is another issue related to the monolithic character of the institutions, (Berlant and Warner, 2002, p.34).

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